

**EXPERIMENTAL AND ANALYTICAL EVALUATION OF A BIAXIAL TEST
FOR DETERMINING IN-PLANE SHEAR PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITES**

John M. Kennedy
(Clemson University, Clemson, SC 29634-0921, USA)
Terry R. Barnett
(Southern Research Institute, Birmingham, AL 35255-5305, USA)
Gary L. Farley
(U. S. Army Aerostructures Directorate, Hampton, VA 23665-5225, USA)

ABSTRACT

The results of an experimental and analytical investigation of a biaxial tension-compression test for determining shear properties of composite materials are reported. The finite element method was used to design the shear test specimens. The resulting test specimen had a large area of pure shear stress whose magnitude equalled that of the applied stress. The stress gradients around the boundary of the test section were small. The geometry was independent of laminate orientation.

A fixture was designed to introduce an equal and opposite pair of forces into a cruciform like specimen. Aluminum and composite laminates were tested in the fixture. The specimens were instrumented in the center of the test section with strain gages to determine shear stress-strain curves. Pure shear strain was measured in the center of the test section. The results from the experiments correlated well with finite element results. Failure of the specimens occurred through the center of the test section and appeared to have initiated at the high stress points on the specimen boundaries. The results showed that a specimen with large corner radii was suitable for determining shear modulus and the nonlinear stress-strain response. Shear strength was conservative because it was influenced by the specimen boundary.

INTRODUCTION

Numerous test methods have been proposed for determining the in-plane shear properties of composite materials. A recent paper by Lee and Munro [1] reviewed many of these shear test methods. A major conclusion of their paper was that none of the test methods produced highly accurate values of elastic shear modulus, stress-strain response, and ultimate shear strength. The inaccuracies of the test methods were due mainly to stress concentrations near the boundaries of the specimen's test section.

Over the past three years, an investigation of several of these shear test methods has been conducted at Clemson University [2]. In this paper, the results of an experimental and analytical investigation of the biaxial tension-compression cruciform specimen are reported. The biaxial loading condition produces a state of pure shear on 45° planes with the magnitude of the theoretical shear stress equal to the magnitude of the applied stress. This method is a modification of the cross-beam test method which has been used to determine shear properties of composites[1]. However, the cross-beam method is not widely used because it requires large quantities of material and the specimen is expensive and complicated to make.

The biaxial tension-compression method is applicable only to laminates with no shear coupling. If the testing apparatus is designed to apply tensile and compressive loads which are equal in magnitude, then the stiffness in the two load directions

must be equal. This condition can be relaxed if a true biaxial test machine is available. (0/90)_s type laminates must be tested to obtain lamina properties, which assumes coupling effects do not influence the shear stress-strain response of the individual plies. Other methods such as the [± 45]_s tensile test also assume no coupling between plies.

In this study, finite element models of the biaxial cruciform shear test specimen were developed to study the effect of specimen geometry on the shear stress distribution in the test section of the specimen and to develop an optimal specimen geometry. A test fixture was developed and numerous specimens were tested.

FINITE ELEMENT MODELS

The models used in the elastic finite element analysis are shown in Fig. 1. The sharp corner model is typical of cross-beam specimens. The model with a corner radius was used to conduct parametric studies to determine how corner geometry effected the stress distribution in the test section. Two-dimensional quadrilateral and triangular, isoparametric membrane elements were used to model the specimen. Because of symmetrical geometry and loading, only one quarter of the specimen was modeled. Isotropic and several orthotropic materials were studied with the model.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

A fixture (unassembled form is shown in Fig. 2) was designed and fabricated to introduce an equal and opposite pair of forces into a specimen. The specimen had a cruciform like configuration with a 25 mm square test section. Each leg of the cross was 25 mm wide and 63 mm long. Tests were run in a standard tensile test machine. Aluminum and composite specimens with sharp corners and a 8.7 mm radius were tested. To determine the shear stress-strain curve, the specimens were instrumented on both sides with three element strain gage rosettes in the center of the test section. Using a room temperature curing structural adhesive, aluminum tabs were bonded to the specimens for load introduction.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Analysis

The finite element results for [± 45]_s cruciform specimen with sharp corners are shown in Fig. 3. These results were consistent with results of Bergner's [3] finite element study. On planes oriented 45° to the load axes, the stress state was pure shear in the center of the test section; however, the region of pure shear was small relative to the size of the test section. Also, the magnitude of the shear stress was greater than the theoretical applied shear stress. There were large stresses and regions of large stress gradients, both normal and shear, at the corners of the test section. Failure of the specimen would likely initiate at the corners of the test section because of the large stresses. In fact, using the two dimensional stresses for each element, Tsai-Wu failure analysis predicted failure to initiate at the sharp corners [4]. These results suggested that the experimentally measured shear stress-strain response of the cruciform specimen with sharp corners, including shear modulus and strength, would probably be incorrect. Furthermore, the size of the region with a pure shear stress state was smaller than most strain gages.

To reduce the high stresses in the corners of the specimen, the sharp corners were replaced with a large radius as depicted in Fig. 1. Stress contours for an isotropic specimen with a corner radius of 8.4 mm are shown in Fig. 4. The magnitude of the shear stress in the center of the specimen was equal to the applied shear stress. The region of uniform pure shear was sufficiently large to bond strain gages. Also, the stress gradients were much smaller than in the specimen with sharp corners. The regions of high normal stress were small relative to size of the test section, and they were far removed from the test section.

The effect of corner radius on the shear stress in the center of the test section is

depicted in Fig. 5. The shear stress in the center of the specimen depended strongly on corner radius and also laminate orientation. The shear stress in the center of a specimen with a corner radius of about 9.0 mm was equal to the applied shear stress for all three laminates considered. Specimens with a larger corner radius had a lower shear stress than specimens with a small corner radius. This trend was reasonable because more material was transmitting the applied loads, and the resulting stresses were lower. If a larger test section were used, the stress gradients, which are boundary dependent, would have little effect on the shear stress in the center of the test section.

2. Experimental

The experimental results showed that the test method worked extremely well. Strain gages showed that the kinematic type fixture generated equal but opposite forces in the legs of the specimen. The strain rosettes showed that the stress state in the center of the specimen was essentially pure shear and oriented at 45° to the legs of the specimen. Typical shear stress-strain curves for a $[\pm 45]_S$ laminate for specimens with sharp and radiused corners are shown in Fig. 6. The elastic stiffness and ultimate strength of the specimen with corner radii was higher than the corresponding values for the specimen with sharp corners. The test method worked equally well for the other laminates tested and the trends were similar [5].

Failure in specimens with sharp corners initiated as cracks in the corners. These cracks propagated across the specimen to opposite corners along the diagonal of the test section. Specimens with corner radii developed a large band of delamination which propagated from diagonally opposite corners into the test section. In both cases failure initiated at the boundary of the test section where the stress gradients were largest. This failure scenario is not representative of an in-plane shear failure.

The nonlinear shear stress-strain response of the specimens with corner radii was probably accurate up to failure, but the failure stress was conservative. The strength of materials that exhibited significant nonlinearity in their shear stress-strain response was probably more accurate than those that exhibited near elastic response because the inelastic behavior limited stress concentrations. The $[\pm 45]_S$ laminate was one of the laminates which had nonlinear response, and this laminate gave the unidirectional or lamina properties.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of an experimental and analytical investigation of a biaxial tension-compression test for determining the in-plane shear properties of composite materials were reported. The effect of specimen geometry on the stress state in the cruciform specimen was studied using finite element analysis. A specimen was designed that produced reasonable elastic modulus and nonlinear stress-strain response. The cruciform specimen with corner radii produced a uniform pure shear stress state over a large region of the test section. The failure mode in the specimens with corner radii was not representative of an in-plane shear failure. Therefore, the measured strength was conservative.

REFERENCES

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a. specimen geometry

b. sharp corner

c. corner radius

Fig. 1. Schematic of specimen geometry and finite element models.

Fig. 2. Photograph of unassembled test fixture and specimen.

a. shear stress, $\tau_{x'y'}$

b. normal stress, $\sigma_{x'}$

c. normal stress, $\sigma_{y'}$

Fig. 3. Normalized stress contours for a $[\pm 45]_S$ cruciform specimen with sharp corners.

a. shear stress, $\tau_{x'y'}$

b. normal stress, $\sigma_{x'}$

c. normal stress, $\sigma_{y'}$

Fig. 4. Normalized stress contours for an isotropic cruciform specimen with 8.4 mm corner radii.

Fig. 5. Variation of the shear stress in the center of the test section with corner radius.

Fig. 6. Shear stress-strain curves for $[\pm 45]_s$ cruciform specimens with sharp corners and 8.7 mm radiused corners.